

Gill pathology of a riverine fish, *Puntius bulu* (Bleeker) infected with myxosporean parasite

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Abstract. Histopathological examinations were made on the gills of a riverine fish, *Puntius bulu*. The gills were found to be severely infected with a myxosporean parasite *Myxobolus* sp. The parasite grew in gill lamellae and formed typical cysts having diameter of 4.86 ± 1.34 μm . The cysts with diameter reaching several times the length of lamella caused extensive pathological changes such as disarrangement of the lamellar structure, obstruction of blood flow and fusion of gill filaments. After maturation, the cyst wall ruptured, releasing the spores. Pathogenicity is attributed to the relative size of cysts, which physically affected the respiratory function of the gill.

INTRODUCTION

Puntius bulu or known locally as tengalan is a native cyprinid freshwater fish of Malaysia and found to be abundant in the natural waters of Pahang and Perak rivers. The fish is also known as tumanggalang in Kelantan and mengalang in Sarawak. This species is a favourite dish amongst the city dwellers especially in Pahang. However, the catch of this species has been reduced drastically due to over fishing activities and destruction of its habitats and spawning ground. As a result of it, the price of the fish has increased from RM10.00 per kilogram in 1980 to RM12.00 per kilogram in 1990 (Tan, 1993). The fish is very susceptible to disease infection. Dykova & Lom (1988) highlighted that, most of the cyprinid fish or carps are prone to myxosporean infection. In fact, many authors had reported on the gill infection with myxosporean (Lom *et al.*, 1983; Dykova & Lom, 1987; Dey *et al.*, 1988; Yokoyama *et*

al., 1992). However, pathological descriptions on the host tissues were scarce. Dykova & Lom (1978) has reported the distortion of the lamellar structure, obstruction of blood flow and fusion of gill filaments by *Myxobolus toyamai* in the common carp. Lom *et al.*, (1983) described dystrophic changes and necrotic disintegration of the gill tissue in the carp, *Cyprinus carpio* infected with *Sphaerospora molnari*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Forty-four tengalan, *P. bulu* were obtained from reservoir dams (Temengor and Kenening) in Perak and also from Pahang rivers (Paya Bugor and Pekan). They varied in size from 12 to 34 cm in body length. Out of this, 20 fishes were used for histopathological study. The fish were killed *in situ* by pithing method and gill tissues were removed and placed in petri dish containing 0.85% normal saline for

examination of parasite. The presence of parasitic infection was confirmed through the smear or scraping of the gill examined under a compound microscope. The method by Lucky (1977) was used for the identification of the cyst and the procedure for spore measurement follows that of Lom & Arthur (1989). As for the iodophilic vacuol structure, Lugol's solution was applied. For histology study, gill tissues were removed, fixed in 10% buffered formalin for 24 - 48 hours, followed by storage in 70% alcohol and processed for paraffin sectioning before staining with haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) as in Humason (1979) method.

RESULTS

Myxosporeans of the genus *Myxobolus* were found in high prevalence in the gill of *Puntius bulu* examined (Fig. 1). Cysts of *Myxobolus* sp. were observed as white nodules in gill lamellae having a size of

$4.86 \pm 1.34 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter. Mature spores are pyriform with slightly acuminate anterior ends and round posterior ends (Fig. 2). The two polar capsules, pyriform in shape, were almost equal in size, and have 5 (4 - 6) coiled threads of the polar filament (Fig. 2A-2C). The measurements were as follows: length of spores is 5.92 ± 0.44 (5-6) μm with width 4.30 ± 0.54 (5-6) μm , while the polar capsule length is 3.66 ± 0.50 (3-4) μm . Initial stages of cyst were located at the tip of secondary gill lamellae forming round-shaped structure surrounded by flattened epithelial cells (Fig. 3). Infected gills exhibited extensive pathological changes caused by the parasite's presence (Fig. 3A-3B and 4A). Multiple cystic growth not only affected the structure of gill lamellae, but also disformed the gill filaments. When matured, the cyst wall ruptured and spores were released (Fig. 3C). In most cases, necrosis of gill lamellae were observed (Fig. 4B) at the site of infection. Large cysts also compressed the adjacent

Figure 1-2. The cysts and spores of *Myxobolus* sp. (1). The cysts of *Myxobolus* sp. (arrow) seen as white nodules on the gills of tengalan, *Puntius bulu*. x15. (2). Spores of *Myxobolus* sp in tengalan. Fresh preparation: (2A). x40; (2B). Immature spores with 5(4-6) coiled threads of polar filament x400. (2C). Mature spore with one of the protruding filament(bar). x400.

uninfected filaments, destroying their normal arrangement and caused atrophy. Blood vessels of the gill were compressed

causing obstruction of the blood flow (Fig. 4C).

Figure 3-4. (3A). Presence of cysts (S), areas of hyperplastic reaction (HP) and gill necrosis (N) in gill filaments due to the *Myxobolus sp.* infection. (3B):Necrosis of the gill lamellae (N) due to the infection of *Myxobolus sp.* (S).(H&E) (x500). (3C): A mature cyst with a thin epithelial cell covering (arrow). Note the pressure necrosis and atrophic area on the adjacent gill lamellae (bold arrow). H&E (x200). (4A). Development of *Myxobolus sp.* in the gills of *Puntius bulu*. First stage of the cyst development. Note the epithelium cell (E) and the obstructed blood capillaries (SD) at the tip of secondary gill filament. H&E (x500). (4B). Developing cyst in the secondary gill lamellae. Note the length of lamella (bar) is equal with the size of cyst (S) and hyperplastic tissue reaction at the base of the gill lamella (x500). (4C). A mature cyst. Note the ballooning cyst (SBP) which is double of the lamella length (bar) and the ruptured cyst with spore released (SP). x500.

DISCUSSION

Results of this study clearly demonstrate that the local tengalan *Puntius bulu* is highly susceptible to infection with myxosporean. All of the examined fish showed infection of the cyst. So far, there is no report on myxosporean infection in the tengalan. The myxosporean observed in this study has two polar capsules with 5 coiled threads and was identified as *Myxobolus* sp. In carp intensive culture system, infection by this group has been reported to cause high mortalities (George, 1987). In Europe similar infection by myxosporean is known as sphaerosporosis. Lom *et al.* (1983), reported that myxospora such as *Spaerospora molnari* caused hyperplasia and lamellae fusion on the gill. The same histopathological changes were observed in the present study. Initially, the *Myxobolus* cyst was located in between the epithelium cells and the blood vessel, appearing as if being captured within. The cyst grew until reaching the base of lamella. At this stage, the spores within the cysts became elongated and the size of the cyst exceeded or was equal to the length of lamella. At this level of pathological changes the *Myxobolus* infection could inevitably affect the respiratory function of the gill by reducing the functional gill area by the mere presence of the large cysts, causing hyperplastic reaction and also obstructing the gill filament's blood circulation. In the later stage, once the cyst ripened and ruptured, it totally destroyed the tissue, resulting in necrotic changes on the gill lamella. This pathological changes could unconditionally cause dyspnic condition in fish. A fish with this condition will be very susceptible to minor degradation of water quality parameters such as low oxygen. Baur (1970) reported that the cyst of myxosporaea (*Myxobolus* sp) could seriously damage the gill filament causing obstruction of blood flow and hyperaemia before necrosis changes occurred.

The finding of this potentially pathogenic parasite in riverine carp is important since they have been reported to cause mortalities and serious epizootics in other carps. Djajadiredja *et al.* (1983) reported that a high percentage of cultured carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) fry were infected with myxosporean and caused great economic losses to Indonesian farmers. Landsberg (1985) also attributed the cause of mortality in carp broodstock in Europe to myxosporean infection.

More than 100 species of *Myxobolus* have been described worldwide (Shulman, 1984). The exact identification of this *Myxobolus* sp. found in *P. bulu* needs further investigation. In conclusion, *Myxobolus* sp. could cause serious mortality as they physically affected the respiratory function of the gill.

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